

Programmable Optical Transmission Systems and Subsystems for Digitized Radio over Fiber

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ABSTRACT:

In this paper we propose a passive optical network based on hybrid wavelength/space division multiplexing for digitized fronthaul delivery, capable to meet the requirements of the future radio access networks. Besides explaining this specific network architecture, we also discuss the different programmable data plane elements. Additionally, we evaluate and demonstrate the support of an extended version of 5G-NR radio signals.

Key words: Passive optical networks, space division multiplexing, wavelength division multiplexing, optical OFDM, optical fronthaul

1.- Introduction

Digitized radio over fibre (DRoF) is a popular fronthaul technology that is being deployed worldwide for giving service to radio access networks (RANs) [1]. This allows centralization with clear advantages in the reduction of CAPEX/OPEX costs in the outside plant, as remote radio units (RRUs) are expected to have smaller installation footprint and energy consumption than a classic base station [1]. However, with the increasing capacity demand of 5G, new radio (5G-NR) waveforms and processing are expected in an environment where small cells are massively deployed at high density [1, 2]. In fact, [2] specifies new radio waveforms featuring increased bandwidth and constellation size, able to cope with capacities beyond 1 Gb/s per user. Since bandwidth and constellation size are increased, DRoF fronthaul should require a significantly large capacity even for transmitting a single radio signal.

This puts DRoF technology at stake, requiring further evolution in order to maintain a certain scalability, while meeting its stringent latency requirements. This need can be addressed with a simple adaptation of DRoF to a new paradigm implying an upgrade of the network fibre plant to include space division

multiplexing (SDM) by deploying multicore fibres (MCFs) [3, 4]. In fact, by the suitable combination of wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) and SDM technologies the total capacity of a RAN can be substantially increased, enabling to setup specific spectral/spatial channels according to the requirements of the services to deliver [5].

An alternative to relax these requirements, consists on decentralizing several radio functions. This is envisioned in the so-called next generation fronthaul interface (NGFI) [6], which proposes to split the different radio functions and implement them in three logical entities: the RRU, the central unit (CU) and the distribution unit (DU). In fact, when approaching NGFI, a flexible functional split is envisioned between CUs and DUs. So, part of the wireless waveforms are generated at the CU and another part at the DUs. In turn, the RAN is split into two different segments. First, the pure fronthaul, which is the segment between RRUs and DUs. Second, the so-called midhaul, which covers the segment between DUs and CUs. This approach enables the use of statistical packet multiplexing while reducing the latency and capacity constraints in the midhaul segment.

Fig. 1: DRoF signal distribution. BVT: bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver; CU: central unit; DU: distributed unit; MCM: multiple core multiplexer; RRU: remote radio head; WSS: wavelength selective switch.

In this paper we review a fronthaul network architecture proposed in [3], detailing the programmable elements and their options in order to accommodate the traffic while optimizing the network resources. Furthermore, we explore the feasibility of digital transmission of extended 5G-NR radio signals.

2.- Main concept

Figure 1 shows a generic scheme hows the general scheme for the SDM based DRoF fronthaul including statistical multiplexing to also approach the NGFI paradigm. There, a central office is attached to an optical metro/core in order to provide connectivity to the network edge. A pool of CUs is envisioned to be connected to the corresponding packet switch whose outputs are connected to either the DUs or the bandwidth/bitrate variable transceivers (BVTs). So, the traffic served over the network corresponds to either the midhaul or fronthaul subnetworks, depending on the specific configuration of the CO and the cell sites. Also a classic fronthaul scheme is envisioned, where the BBUs are placed in the central office and the corresponding traffic is also served over the network down to the cell sites.

The CO is meant to allow different traffic routing schemes depending on the architec-

ture implemented at the cell sites: spatial multiplexing, spectral multiplexing, and spectral/spatial multiplexing.

Spatial multiplexing refers to a strategy where the cell sites have only SDM capabilities, and each cell site is served by a specific wavelength in different cores (no spectral multiplexing is used for serving those sites). This is highlighted in Fig. 1 (a). In case using BVTs based on direct detection (which is the main approach for cost effectiveness) a specific optical filter should be present at the BVTs of the cell site.

Similarly, spectral multiplexing is the case when each cell site is served by a specific core and different wavelengths. A cell site scheme for this approach is shown in Fig. 1 (b) and (c). Fig. 1 (b) shows a scheme employing arrayed waveguide grating (AWG) for wavelength demultiplexing/multiplexing according to a fixed grid, while Fig. 1 (c) shows a scheme employing a flexible wavelength selective switch (WSS) for the same purpose according to a flexible grid.

Fig. 1 (d) shows a generic case, where spatial and/or spectral multiplexing is used in order to deliver the radio access network traffic. Please note that in this case we also envision the transmission of packetized information

according to NGFI paradigm. Therefore, packet (statistical) multiplexing is also included in this case.

As for the signal duplexing, different strategies can be followed. In fact, either SDM or WDM duplex can be approached, depending on the specific network design. For example, in a pure spatial multiplexing, each cell site has a specific wavelength assigned and, thus, an SDM-based duplex should be considered. Similarly, in a pure spectral multiplexing a WDM-based duplex would be desirable, since each cell site has a specific core assigned.

In order to cope with such network routing diversity, different optical network elements and subsystems are used at the CO and the different flavors of cell site: The BVTs, the optical switching matrix of the CO and the different WSSs.

The BVTs are the main elements for DRoF transmission. An option for implementing the required BVTs can be based DD-OFDM. In fact, this option is one of the most attractive for cost-effectively coping with the flexibility requirements of the network [7]. In fact, OFDM provides advanced spectrum manipulation capabilities, including arbitrary sub-carrier suppression and bit/power loading. Thanks to these features, DD-OFDM transceivers can be ad hoc configured for achieving a certain reach and/or coping with a targeted data rate adopting low complex optoelectronic subsystems.

The optical switching matrix of the CO is in charge of connecting the inputs/outputs of each BVT to the corresponding WSSs and, thus, the different fiber cores. A high port count optical switching matrix should be employed to obtain a high degree of flexibility. Nevertheless, a more practical implementation could rely on limiting the number of ports by appropriately dimensioning the network traffic. In case this would not be possible, an alternative would be to either approach a series of low port count matrices and/or directly interface the WSSs with a convenient number of BVTs. In terms of programmability, this element also needs a specific control agent in order to allow the network SDN controller to effectively route

the traffic over the network by establishing the appropriate port connections of the matrix.

The output ports of the switching matrix are connected to the WSSs, which are performing the wavelength division multiplexing or demultiplexing of the different signals into arbitrary portions of the spectrum according to the control plane indications. In fact, a control agent is needed for controlling these devices, so that SDN controller is able to set a specific frequency slot for one or several transceivers in a specific core, depending on the type of cell sites to serve. Even the ideal devices would be flexible WSSs in order to direct the traffic with a high degree of flexibility, in practice other wavelength multiplexing and/or demultiplexing elements can be used, like fixed AWGs. In that case the assignment of the spectral channels is performed only by tuning the BVTs to the desired wavelength and connecting the appropriate ports of the optical switching matrix.

Since the optical distribution network is entirely passive, the SDN controller should be able to efficiently route the traffic by configuring the CO and the different cell sites by means of the interaction with the control agents of the BVTs, the optical switch matrix and, eventually, the WSSs.

3.- Implementation

The key elements for the radio signal evaluation are the fronthaul digital transmitters and receivers shown in Fig. 2. The fronthaul digital transmitter (FTx) is composed of a radio signal generation stage, where a digital radio signal is generated according to the parameters of Table 1. Even 5G-NR specifies signals up to 400 MHz, in our case we consider an extension of the standard by combining the maximum subcarrier spacing and maximum number of subcarriers. This signal is then sampled at 983.04 MHz and digitized at M bits per sample, with M ranging between 4 and 20. It is worth noting that before actual digitization, the radio signal is clipped at ± 3 times its standard deviation in order to ensure a normalized and unbiased digitization scale. The resulting IQ samples are mapped following the CPRI principles [8, 9]. The resulting

Fig. 2 Fronthaul digital transmitter/receiver schemes.

Table 1 Extended 5G-NR radio parameters for FTx/FRx

Parameter	Value
Subcarrier spacing	240 kHz
Num. of points for FFT	4096
Sampling frequency (f_s)	983.04 MHz
Number of subcarriers	3168
Constellation	256-QAM

bit stream is framed also following the procedures specified in [8]. For example, in case $M=10$, every 5120 bits (256 IQ samples) a 344-bit word is included for control and monitoring purposes. These control and monitoring words are simple random bits generated for taking into account the associated overhead. The resulting data is then injected into the corresponding transceivers.

At the fronthaul digital receiver (FRx), incoming data is deframed while removing the control and monitoring words. Next, IQ samples are demapped from the resulting bits, and the radio signal is reconstructed; ready to be converted to the analogue domain, further amplified and radiated.

3.1.- Preliminary evaluation

The blocks of Fig. 2 have been implemented as a library in Python. A preliminary evaluation is performed in order to evaluate its performance limits and relationship between the figures of merit of DRoF and ARoF. Therefore, an ideal additive white Gaussian noise channel is considered between FTx and FRx blocks of Fig. 2. 256 OFDM radio frames are generated and processed accordingly. BER

Fig. 3: EVM floor as function of the number of bits per sample (M).

has been computed by error counting at the input of FRx, while EVM has been computed after radio signal detection. Different radio signal constellations have been tested according to Table 1.

Results are shown in Figures 3 and 4. There we observe an EVM floor due to signal clipping and the inherent quantization associated to the signal digitization. As expected, this EVM floor decreases rapidly when increasing the number of bits per sample (M), converging to values below 0.1% for all the constellations tested. Interestingly, $M=10$ can be set as the limit to ensure these values. This becomes relevant in Fig. 4, where the results for 256QAM modulation are depicted. There curves for $M=10$ up to $M=20$ are on top of each other.

Regarding target EVM values before the radiation elements (after power amplifiers), they are of 12.5% for 16QAM, 8% for 64QAM and 3.5% for 256QAM [2]. Since power amplifiers have typical noise figures of 4.5dB [10], the targeted EVM at the output of FRx block is expected to be 7.5% for 16QAM, 4.8% for 64QAM and 2.1% for

Fig. 4: EVM as function of BER for 256QAM and different number of bits per sample (M).

256QAM. Therefore, in terms of EVM floor limit, the system is compliant with those values for 16QAM and 64QAM, while 256QAM is limited to operate with values of M above 5. In terms of BER for the 256QAM case (the most restrictive), we should ensure BER below $2.63 \cdot 10^{-4}$ when considering $M \geq 10$.

3.2.- Experimental evaluation

Once seen the limits of the digitization and EVM as function of BER, we proceed to evaluate the performance of the system when emulating the network infrastructure depicted in Fig. 1.

An assessment of DRoF transmission of 256-QAM 760.32 MHz radio signal is reported in [11]. There, a radio signal featuring total capacity of 6.13 Gb/s is digitized to a 22.25 Gb/s DRoF data stream and transmitted over a passive network composed by 40-wavelength 100-GHz AWGs and a 25.4 km 19-core fiber. Results show EVM figures lower than the target 2.1 %, while covering a

power budget of 26.5 dB, and 26 dB even in presence of core-to-core crosstalk.

4.- Conclusion

We propose a hybrid WDM/SDM passive optical network based for digital fronthaul delivery. In fact, the different programmable components are discussed, while the support of extended 5G-NR radio signals is evaluated and demonstrated.

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